

Chip-Scale Wavelength-Division Multiplexed Integrated Sensor Arrays

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Abstract—We demonstrate a wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) technique for interrogating multiple sensors on a single chip. While wavelength- and frequency-division multiplexing (FDM) has previously been demonstrated in micro-electro-mechanical (MEMS) sensors, numerous off-chip components were required thereby increasing the system size and limiting the number of sensors. In contrast, our approach enables all components to be developed on-chip. The high Q-factor afforded by optical microcavities enables a large number of sensor elements to be interrogated using WDM. First, we demonstrate wavelength-enabled addressing of individual sensors. Next, we show how two sensors can be individually interrogated in a sensor network. Finally, we illustrate how such “sensor-networks on a chip” are fabricated. The ability to develop large-scale arrays, where each sensor has been functionalized to respond to a different analyte, enables increased selectivity for MEMS resonant chemical sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) are an attractive technology for miniaturized sensor arrays. Due to their small size, MEMS resonators are very sensitive to small changes in their mass. The sensors rely on absorption of analytes, mass loading, and resonant frequency shift [1]. By coating multiple sensors with different chemo-selective polymers, where each polymer absorbs only a particular analyte, highly selective sensor arrays can be developed.

Readout of the sensor’s mechanical resonant frequency can be performed electrically or optically. In particular, optical readout offers the advantage of high signal to noise ratio. By combining MEMS resonators with optical microcavities (e.g. Fabry-Perot interferometers), multiple sensors can be read out individually. In such a wavelength-division-multiplexing (WDM) approach, each optical micro-cavity is designed to have a unique optical resonant wavelength. By tuning the wavelength of the readout laser to correspond to the optical resonant wavelength of a particular sensor, each sensor in the array can be individually addressed.

Previously, WDM was demonstrated using commercial fiber-Bragg grating (FBG) or arrayed-waveguide grating

(AWG) components [2]. While such systems are effective for individual interrogation of multiple sensors, they require several off-chip components. Also, each sensor comprises a separate chip, which limits the sensor array size. We previously demonstrated single-chip vertical optical cavity MEMS sensor arrays, where each sensor had a different mechanical resonant frequency (frequency-division-multiplexing or FDM) [3]. Arrays with four sensors were demonstrated, but larger arrays are complicated by the increase in required optical power. While mechanical Q-factors are generally modest due to air damping (the sensors need to be operated at atmospheric pressures), optical Q’s can be extremely high. Therefore, optical WDM enables a larger number of sensors to be interrogated compared to FDM. Recently, we demonstrated a MEMS sensor with integrated waveguide Fabry-Perot microcavity [4] and now demonstrate a WDM technique for chip-scale sensor arrays.

Figure 1. Schematic of sensor indicating MEMS resonator and Fabry-Perot microcavity (not to scale); inset: image of fabricated sensor (false color). The transmitted (T_x) and reflected (R_x) signals give equivalent information.

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Figure 2. Measured transmitted and reflected Fabry-Perot optical spectrum for two sensors: a) measurement setup with fiber circulator to separate input and reflected light, b) *sensor 1* with Fabry-Perot cavity length $L_{C1}=100\ \mu\text{m}$ and $FSR=3.5\ \text{nm}$, c) *sensor 2* with $L_{C2}=6\ \mu\text{m}$ and $FSR=50\ \text{nm}$.

II. SENSOR APPROACH

The sensors' operating principal relies on chemical absorption and mass loading [1, 3-4]. Our sensor has been described in detail in [4]. Briefly, individual sensors comprise a silicon microbridge resonator, square paddles placed along the length of the microbridge, a rib waveguide perpendicular to the MEMS resonator, and two silicon/air distributed Bragg reflectors (DBR's), as shown in Fig. 1. The paddles are coated with a chemo-selective polymer for analyte sorption and hence mass-loading of the microbridge resonator. Any resonant frequency shift is proportional to mass-loading which in turn is proportional to the concentration of analyte present in the environment. The DBR mirrors form a Fabry-Perot optical microcavity. One of the DBR's is fixed while the second DBR is attached to the center of the suspended microbridge. In this manner, the microbridge oscillation modulates the Fabry-Perot cavity transmission (actuation can be electrostatic [4] or optical [3]); tuning the laser wavelength near the Fabry-Perot mode, where the slope $\partial/\partial\lambda$ is maximum, enables optical readout of the mechanical resonant frequency with high precision.

Individual sensors are coated with a unique chemo-selective polymer and will – ideally – only respond to a

distinct chemical analyte. In order to sense multiple analytes present in the environment simultaneously, sensor arrays are required. One technique to distinguish multiple sensors is to use frequency-division-multiplexing [3]. In this approach, each sensor has a different resonant frequency, thereby enabling simple identification of each sensor's response. A drawback is the relatively low mechanical Q-factor (typically 10^2 - 10^3 in air due to viscous or squeeze-film damping), which limits the number of sensors that can be interrogated due to frequency bandwidth limitations.

An alternative approach uses wavelength-division-multiplexing. Optical Q-factors can be extremely high (10^4 - 10^8) so that wavelength multiplexing enables many signals to occupy only a small optical bandwidth. The Fabry-Perot microcavities are inherently wavelength selective. We can design each sensor to have a unique optical resonant wavelength by varying the Fabry-Perot cavity length, L_C . Fig. 2 shows the measured optical spectra for two sensors with $L_{C1}=100\ \mu\text{m}$ and $L_{C2}=6\ \mu\text{m}$. A tunable laser sweeps the input wavelength and maps out the optical resonance. Lensed fibers are used for efficient input/output coupling to/from the device. We use a fiber circulator to separate the input and reflected signal (Fig. 2a). The transmitted signal is measured using a second lensed fiber at the device output waveguide. Both the transmitted (T_X) and reflected (R_X) signal (defined in Fig. 1) give equivalent information according to $T_X=1-R_X-L$, where L is the cavity loss. The free-spectral range (FSR) is 3.5 nm and 50 nm for *sensor 1* and *sensor 2*, respectively. We note that the two measured Fabry-Perot spectra result in unique wavelengths where $\partial/\partial\lambda$ is maximum for *sensor 1* and zero for *sensor 2* (i.e. $\lambda_{ON,SENSOR 1}=\lambda_{OFF,SENSOR 2}=1538.7\ \text{nm}$ in Fig. 2). Similarly, a unique wavelength $\lambda_{ON,SENSOR 2}$ exists for addressing *sensor 2*.

III. WAVELENGTH ENABLED SENSOR ADDRESSING

In Fig. 2 we showed the measured Fabry-Perot optical response for two sensors with different cavity lengths. In order to selectively measure the mechanical resonance of a particular sensor, we set our laser to a wavelength where $\partial/\partial\lambda$ is maximum or zero. Initially, we measure each sensor individually using the setup in Fig. 3a. All experiments are performed at atmospheric pressure. The measurement is similar to Fig. 2a, but with the addition of a network analyzer that supplies a frequency-swept actuation voltage to drive the MEMS beam to resonance. The detected optical signal is sent to the analyzer and plotted as a function of frequency. At resonance, the MEMS beam has maximum displacement; consequently, the Fabry-Perot cavity exhibits maximum modulation depth when the MEMS bridge is on resonance.

Fig. 3b,c show the mechanical resonance for *sensor 1* and *sensor 2*, respectively. *Sensor 1* is measured at two wavelengths, $\lambda_{ON}=1605.0\ \text{nm}$ and $\lambda_{OFF}=1445.0\ \text{nm}$ while *sensor 2* has $\lambda_{ON}=1569.0\ \text{nm}$ and $\lambda_{OFF}=1491.1\ \text{nm}$. Both sensors are measured using a drive actuation voltage of 1.4 V_{pp}. The measurements show that we can selectively interrogate each sensor by tuning to an appropriate wavelength, where $\partial/\partial\lambda$ is maximum or zero. The signal contrast between λ_{ON} and λ_{OFF} is better than 20 dB, limited mainly by the modest optical Q in the present devices.

Figure 3. a) Experiment schematic, b) measured transmitted and reflected mechanical resonant spectrum for *sensor 1* for two wavelengths λ_{ON} and λ_{OFF} , c) mechanical resonant spectrum for *sensor 2*.

IV. WAVELENGTH DIVISION MULTIPLEXED SENSOR ARRAYS

In the previous section we demonstrated wavelength-selective interrogation of individual sensors. The next step towards developing sensor arrays is to interconnect multiple sensors with a single optical input/output. By tuning the laser to an appropriate wavelength, each sensor in the array can be individually addressed. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 4a. As a proof-of-concept, we use off-chip 1×2 fiber couplers as power splitters/combiners to interconnect two separate sensor chips (*sensor 1* and *sensor 2* from Fig. 3). Light from a single tunable laser is split into two arms and coupled to the two sensor chips via lensed optical fibers. The light is then collected from the two chips via a second pair of lensed fibers, combined using a fiber coupler, and sent to a single photodetector. A network analyzer sends a frequency-swept actuation voltage to both sensors simultaneously. By tuning the laser wavelength to λ_{ON} for a particular sensor, we can selectively interrogate each sensor independently provided that the slope $\partial/\partial\lambda$ is maximum for *sensor 1* and zero for *sensor 2*.

Figure 4. a) Sensor network experiment schematic, b) measured transmitted mechanical resonant spectrum for *sensor 1* and *sensor 2*.

Fig. 4b shows the wavelength-division-multiplexing sensor measurement. The drive actuation voltage was $1.4 V_{PP}$ swept over a frequency range $f=30-230$ kHz. By tuning the laser to a wavelength $\lambda_{ON, Sensor 1}=1538.7$ nm, we can measure the response of *sensor 1*. We note that this wavelength corresponds to $\lambda_{OFF, Sensor 2}$, thereby ensuring that there is no response from *sensor 2* (see Fabry-Perot spectra in Fig. 2). The mechanical resonance spectrum shows a peak at $f_0=146.5$ kHz, which is in good agreement with the measurement in Fig. 3, confirming that this is the *sensor 1* response. Similarly, we can tune the probe laser wavelength to $\lambda_{ON, Sensor 2}=\lambda_{OFF, Sensor 1}=1465.69$ nm, which gives a resonant frequency $f_0=88$ kHz. Comparing the result with the measurement in Fig. 3b confirms that this is the response from *sensor 2*. We note that in these proof-of-concept experiments the devices were designed to have different mechanical resonant frequencies to enable simple identification of each sensor's response. Future devices can be designed with identical mechanical resonant frequencies since wavelength-division-multiplexing ensures orthogonal measurement of each sensor's response, as demonstrated in Fig. 4.

V. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

A. On-chip waveguide splitters

Our initial measurements were performed using off-chip fiber couplers and two sensor chips. The results demonstrate that we can take advantage of the wavelength-selective properties of the Fabry-Perot cavity for highly-sensitive displacement and resonant frequency measurement as well as wavelength-selective interrogation.

In order to develop large-scale integrated sensor arrays we require on-chip waveguide splitters for power

splitting/combining. The basic architecture is shown in Fig. 5. It is similar to Fig. 4a, except with the replacement of the off-chip fiber couplers with on-chip Y-branch waveguides and two sensors on a single chip. Waveguide splitters can be made with low loss – we have demonstrated splitters with <0.5 dB excess loss and even lower loss has been demonstrated by others [5]; therefore, many devices can be interconnected into a “sensor array on a chip.” A potential drawback with this approach is that the power to each sensor will be reduced to P_{IN}/N , where P_{IN} is the power in the input waveguide and N is the number of sensors. An alternative approach is to use add-drop filters [6], where power splitting is not an issue since only specific wavelengths are “dropped.”

B. Sensor Coatings

In this work we have studied uncoated sensors to demonstrate the basic concept of chip-scale wavelength-division-multiplexing for large-scale sensor arrays. We previously discussed and demonstrated a technique for coating the sensors with chemo-selective polymers [4] and demonstrated coating multiple sensors with different chemo-selective polymers in order to detect multiple analytes [3]. Future chip-scale sensor arrays, as shown in Fig. 5, will need to be coated in a similar manner.

C. Mechanical Q-factor

The mechanical Q-factors for our sensors are modest ($Q_M \approx 10$ in air), which limits the minimum resonant frequency shift and hence mass-loading that can be measured. Measurements performed with pressures in the range 20 mTorr – atmosphere have shown that the low mechanical Q-factor is the result of squeeze-film and viscous damping. Indeed, we have measured mechanical $Q_M > 10^4$ for similar devices at 22 mTorr [7]. We expect $Q_M = 10^2 - 10^3$ should be possible in air, provided that the air gaps for actuating the devices can be increased to limit squeeze-film damping.

D. Cavity Opto-Mechanics for All-Optical Sensors

A further improvement in our sensor array can be obtained by taking advantage of cavity opto-mechanics [8, 9]. The high-intensity optical field inside the Fabry-Perot cavity can be used to apply an optical force that changes the behavior of the MEMS resonator. The optical force can modify the MEMS spring constant and increase the effective mechanical Q. Using such opto-mechanical interaction, we have increased the effective mechanical Q-factor from 2×10^4 to 5×10^5 [7] (measured at 22 mTorr pressure). Accompanied with this increase in mechanical Q-factor is a strong increase in vibration amplitude so that electrostatic actuation is no longer required. This enables all-optical sensors that can be actuated and interrogated using a single CW laser.

CONCLUSION

A WDM technique was demonstrated for interrogating individual sensors in a large-scale sensor array. Proof-of-concept measurements were performed using off-chip fiber couplers. The fabrication of a single-chip sensor array with WDM capability was presented. Various other device improvements were also discussed.

Figure 5. Partially fabricated demonstration single-chip two-sensor array (false-color). The fiber couplers are replaced by on-chip Y-branch waveguides. Sensor 1 and 2 were designed with different Fabry-Perot cavity lengths. N-branch waveguides can be used for N-sensor arrays ($N > 2$).

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